

PHOTO-OXIDATION OF QUININE.

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The photo-oxidation of quinine hydrochloride by uranyl nitrate, sodium vanadate and potassium dichromate has been studied. Differences have been obtained for the velocity of photoreduction of vanadate by quinine in *d* and *l*-circularly polarised light.

Complex Formation.—Uranyl nitrate enhances the rotation of quinine hydrochloride, $C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_2$, HCl , $2H_2O$. Measurements of the rotation of these mixtures, keeping the concentration of quinine hydrochloride constant, showed that the rotation of the mixtures attained a maximum value for mixtures of the composition quinine-4-uranyl; further increase in concentration of uranyl had no effect on the maximal rotation. Assuming that for these optimum mixtures (*i.e.* for which the maximal rotations just begin) complex formation is complete, *i.e.* concentration of complex = concentration of quinine, the dissociation constant of the complex

$$K = \frac{[\text{Complex}]}{[\text{Quinine-complex}] \times [\text{uranyl-complex}]}$$

was calculated according to the method described for tartaric acid-uranyl nitrate mixtures in a previous paper (Rama Char, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 351). The results are given below.

TABLE I.

Length of solution = 2.5 cm. $\lambda = 5893\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of quinine hydrochloride = 0.025M.				Conc. of quinine hydrochloride = 0.0125M.			
Conc. of uranyl.	Obs. rotation.	Conc. of complex.	K.	Conc. of uranyl.	Obs. rotation.	Conc. of complex.	K.
0.100M	-0.60°	0.025M		0.050	-0.30	0.0125	
0.050	-0.54	0.019	102	0.028	-0.26	0.008	100
0.025	-0.49	0.014	115	0.012	-0.23	0.005	102
0.013	-0.44	0.008	94	0.006	-0.21	0.003	110
—	-0.36	—	—	—	-0.18	—	—
Mean value							104

There is concordance in the values of *K* and the sign of rotation of the complex is the same as that of quinine.

Photoreaction.—The complex obtained by the addition of uranyl nitrate to quinine hydrochloride is photo-sensitive and undergoes reduction in the ultraviolet, quinine being oxidised and the uranyl salt reduced to the uranous state: $U^{VI}_{(yellow)} \rightarrow U^{IV}_{(green)}$. The experimental arrangement for studying the photoreaction was the same as that described in a previous paper (Rama Char, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 507).

The reaction was followed by estimating the uranous content by the König-Marten spectrophotometer. For this purpose standard uranyl solution was completely reduced in an atmosphere of CO_2 to the uranous state by adding the calculated amount of titanous chloride. The uranous concentration in the blackish green solution thus obtained was estimated according to the method described in a previous paper by the author (Rama Char, 1942, *loc cit.*).

Different sets of mixtures of uranous solution and quinine hydrochloride were then made up, the concentration of quinine being the same for a set but varying from one set to another. The absorption of these mixtures in the blue region was then measured spectrophotometrically. The molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ is given by,

$$\epsilon = (\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1) / c.d.$$

where θ_2 and θ_1 are the spectro-readings with solution and water respectively, c , the molar concentration of solution and d , the length of solution in cm. The measurements showed that the absorption of the mixture in each set was independent of the concentration of quinine and depended only upon the uranous concentration. The results obtained for a few typical mixtures are given below.

TABLE II.

Length of solution = 0.5 cm. $\lambda = 4916 \text{ \AA}$.

Conc. of uranous.	($\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$) in conc. of quinine.		
	0.025M.	0.013M.	0.006M.
0.020M	0.515	0.515	0.515
0.013	0.372	0.372	0.372
0.006	0.213	0.213	0.213
0.003	0.139	0.147	0.139

The concentration of uranous when plotted against ($\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$) gave a straight line (diagram not shown), and from this the concentration of uranous in any unknown mixture could be found out by knowing the spectro-reading.

There is no dark reaction in 24 hours and the photoreaction is zero-molecular with respect to uranyl. The results obtained are given below. dx/dt refers throughout to the number of g. mois transformed per minute.

TABLE III.

Radiation = complete ultraviolet. $p_n = 3$ to 4. Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of quinine.	Conc. of uranyl.	I_{abs} .	dx/dt .	$k = dx/dt / I_{abs}$
0.025M	0.500M	20070 ergs	5.0×10^{-8}	25.0×10^{-10}
"	0.100	"	5.0	25.0
"	"	10380	2.5	24.0
"	0.050	17300	4.3	24.9
0.013	"	"	4.3	24.9
"	0.025	"	4.3	24.9
"	"	8650	2.2	25.4
0.006	0.023	17300	4.2	24.3
0.003	0.010	"	4.3	24.9
0.001	0.004	"	4.3	24.9
	0.002	"	4.2	24.3

The results show that in spite of the large variation in the concentration of the reactants, the velocity of the reaction is simply proportional to the intensity of the light absorbed by the complex.

$$dx/dt = k \times I_{abs}, \quad \text{where } k = 24.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ (mean value).}$$

Quinine Vanadate Sol.

Quinine vanadate sol was prepared by peptising the freshly precipitated quinine vanadate obtained by the addition of quinine hydrochloride to sodium meta-vanadate. It was then filtered when a colourless sol was obtained. This was quite stable for several days and did not coagulate.

This sol is photo-sensitive to ultraviolet light (3130Å) and undergoes reduction when exposed to this radiation; quinine is oxidised and vanadium reduced from the pentavalent to the quadrivalent state. The reaction was followed by estimating the vanadium (as V^{4+}) according to the method of Furman (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 314). There is no dark reaction in 18 hours and the photoreaction is zero-molecular with respect to pentavalent vanadium. The results obtained are given below,

TABLE IV.

$$\lambda = 3130\text{\AA}. \quad \phi_s = 7.1. \quad \text{Temp.} = 25^\circ. \quad k = (dx/dt)/I_{\text{abs}} \times [\text{sol}].$$

Conc. of quinine : conc. of NaVO_3 in sol = 1:7.

Conc. of sol. as V^v .	I_{abs} .	dx/dt .	k .	Quantum efficiency (γ).
0.023M	4560 ergs	7.9×10^{-8}	7.5×10^{-8}	0.05
0.012	"	8.9	7.1	0.03
0.023	9120	15.8	7.5	

The velocity of the reaction can be expressed by the equation.

$$dx/dt = k \times I_{\text{abs}} \times [\text{sol}], \quad \text{where } k = 7.4 \times 10^{-8}.$$

The quantum efficiency of the photo-process is small.

Reaction in Circularly Polarised Light.—Quinine vanadate sol exhibits circular dichroism in the ultraviolet ($3130\text{\AA}$), the anisotropy factor g being positive. This means that the molecular extinction coefficient of the sol in l -circularly polarised light is greater than that in d -light, and therefore, the velocity of the photoreduction of the sol in l -light is expected to be greater than that in d -light. The experimental results conform to these expectations. Circularly polarised light was obtained by the combinations of a Glans polarising prism and a Carl Zeiss quarter-wave plate. The circular dichroism was measured according to a method involving the sensitive Moll thermopile relay system with a Zernicke galvanometer. (The details are described in a paper to be published shortly). The values obtained for the circular dichroism of the sol and for the velocity of the photoreduction are given below.

TABLE V.

Conc. of sol as $V^v = 0.023M$ $\epsilon_l = \text{Mol.}$
extinction coeff. in l -circularly polarised light. $\epsilon_d = \text{Mol.}$ extinction
coeff. in d -circularly polarised light.
Other conditions same as in Table
IV.

Wave-length.	$g = (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_d) / \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_l + \epsilon_d)$.
$3130\text{\AA}$	+0.011

TABLE VI.

Conc. of sol as $V^v = 0.023M$
 $\lambda = 3930\text{\AA}$. Other conditions same
as in Table IV.

Polarised light.	I_{abs} .	dx/dt .
l -circular	1380 ergs	2.7×10^{-8} .
d "	"	1.8

The velocity of the reaction in l -light is greater than that in d -light, and the difference in the value of dx/dt is very large.

Quinine Dichromate Sol.

Quinine dichromate sol was prepared, as in the case of quinine vanadate sol by peptising the freshly precipitated quinine dichromate obtained by the addition of quinine hydrochloride to potassium dichromate. It was then filtered when an yellow or orange coloured sol was obtained. This was quite stable for several days and did not coagulate.

The sol is photo-sensitive to ultraviolet ($3130\text{\AA}$) as well as to visible light ($4060\text{\AA}$ and $4360\text{\AA}$) and undergoes reduction when exposed to these radiations. Quinine is oxidised and dichromate reduced: $\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}_{(\text{yellow})} \rightarrow \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}_{(\text{green})}$. The reaction was followed by the iodimetric method for the estimation of dichromate. There is no dark reaction in 15 hours, and the photoreaction is zero-molecular with respect to dichromate.

The experimental results given in Table VII below show that they are of the same type as those obtained for the photo-reduction of quinine vanadate sol.

TABLE VII.

$\lambda = 3130\text{\AA}$. $\rho_{21} = 5.3$. Temp. = 25° . $k = (dx/dt)/I_{\text{abs}} \times [\text{sol}]$.
Conc. of quinine : conc. of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in sol = 1:3.

Conc. of sol as dichromate.	I_{abs} .	dx/dt .	k .	Quantum efficiency (η).
0.012M	9950 ergs	3.6×10^{-6}	3.0×10^{-8}	0.012
0.006	"	1.7	2.9	0.006
0.012	5280	1.8	2.8	
"	3290	1.2	3.0	

Contrary to the observations of Forbes *et al* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 960) it has been found that the sol undergoes photoreduction in blue light. Tables VIII and IX give the results obtained in the violet and blue regions.

TABLE VIII.

$\lambda = 3060\text{\AA}$. Other conditions same as in Table VII.

Conc. of sol.	I_{abs} .	dx/dt .	k .	η .
0.012M	8650 ergs	2.7×10^{-6}	2.6×10^{-8}	0.008
0.006	"	1.4	2.7	0.004
0.012	6490	2.0	2.6	
"	4320	1.4	2.7	

TABLE IX.

 $\lambda = 4360\text{\AA}$. (Other conditions same as in Table VII.)

Conc. of sol.	I_{abs} .	dx/dt .	k .	γ .
0.012M	7780 ergs	2.4×10^{-6}	2.6×10^{-11}	0.007
0.006	"	1.2	2.6	0.004
0.012	4840	1.5	2.6	

Tables VII, VIII and IX show that the quantum efficiency of the photo-process is small ; it decreases with increasing wave-length of the radiation.

The velocity of the photoreduction of quinone dichromate. sol in the ultraviolet, violet and blue regions can be expressed by the equation

$$dx/dt = k \times I_{abs} \times [\text{sol}].$$

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